

The Influence of Flock Age of Broiler Breeder on Egg Water Loss Incubation Duration and Chick Development

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ABSTRACT

Broiler breeder age influences quality traits of incubating egg, incubation duration and embryo/chick development. Eggs obtained from Ross 308 broiler breeder genotype at 30 weeks of age, 40 weeks of age, 43 weeks of age, 51 weeks of age and 57 weeks of age were incubated. Prior to incubation, the quality traits of eggs were determined and individually weighed in order to calculate relative egg water loss at 18th day of incubation. External pipping and hatching times were determined between 450 and 520 hours of incubation.

The findings have demonstrated that the quality characteristics of pre-incubation hatching eggs exhibit a direct linear relationship with increasing breeding age. Egg water loss of eggs in 40 weeks of age was significantly higher, while it was significantly lower in 43 weeks of age than eggs from the other ages. The longest external pipping and hatching times were obtained at weeks 30 and 51 of age, whereas the shortest external pipping and hatching times were at weeks 40 and 57 of age. The heaviest and the longest chicks were obtained from the oldest breeders. In conclusion, the characteristics of the eggs that are used in the hatching process, and which are related to the age of the breeder, have a significant impact on both the length of the incubation period related to egg water loss and the subsequent development of the chicks.

Key words: broiler breeder, breeder age, incubation duration, external pipping, egg water loss.

Broiler damızlık sürü yaşının yumurta su kaybı, kuluçka süresi ve civciv gelişimi üzerine etkisi

ÖZ

Etlik damızlık tavukların yaşı, kuluçkalık yumurtanın kalite özelliklerini, kuluçka süresini ve embriyo/civciv gelişimini etkiler. Ross 308 genotipin 30 haftalık, 40 haftalık, 43 haftalık, 51 haftalık ve 57 haftalık yaşlarından elde edilen yumurtalar kuluçkalanmıştır. Kuluçkadan önce yumurtanın kalite özellikleri belirlenmiş ve her bir yumurtanın ağırlığı tartılmış ve aynı tartım kuluçkanın 18. gününde yumurta su kaybını hesaplamak amacıyla tekrarlanmıştır. Embriyonun kabuğu delme ve kabuktan çıkma süreleri kuluçkanın 450 ile 520. saatleri arasında belirlenmiştir.

Bulgular, kuluçkadan önce kuluçkalık yumurtaların kalite özelliklerinin damızlık yaşının artmasıyla doğrudan ilişki gösterdiğini ortaya koymuştur. Kırk haftalık yaştaki yumurtaların su kaybı diğer yaş gruplarına göre önemli düzeyde daha yükseken, 43 haftalık yumurtalarda ise daha düşük olmuştur. En uzun dış kabuk çatlama ve kuluçka süreleri 30 ve 51 haftalık yaşların yumurtalarında elde edilirken, en kısa süreler ise 40 ve 57 haftalık yumurtalarda kaydedildi. En ağır ve en uzun civcivler en yaşlı damızlıklardan elde edilmiştir. Sonuç olarak, kuluçka sürecinde kullanılan ve damızlığın yaşıyla ilişkili olan yumurta özellikleri, hem yumurta su kaybıyla ilgili kuluçka süresinin uzunluğu hem de civcivlerin gelişimi üzerinde önemli bir etkiye sahiptir.

Anahtar kelimeler: etlik damızlık, damızlık yaşı, kuluçka süresi, kabuğu delme, yumurta su kaybı

INTRODUCTION

The quality of hatched chick is under the effects of less-well-understood factors such as breeder age and egg storage before incubation (Tona et al. 2004). Broiler breeder age influences embryogenesis and then subsequent broiler performance (Peebles et al. 1999; Peebles et al. 2001), total incubation length and hatchability of eggs (Latour et al. 1996; Hudson et al. 2004; Luquetti et al. 2004; Yalçın et al. 2006; Yalçın et al. 2008), metabolic rate of embryo (O’dea et al. 2004) and body composition of chick at hatch (Peebles et al. 2001; Babacanoğlu et al. 2007). The increased breeder age is related to increased development rate (O’dea et al. 2004) and residual yolk sac weight (Peebles et al. 2000), and longer chick length (Babacanoğlu et al. 2007) and shorter incubation time (Noy and Sklan 1997).

Broiler breeder age has significant effects on weight of the incubating egg which is directly related to the weight of newly hatched chicks (Shanawany 1984; Yannakopoulos and Tserveni-Gousi 1987). Babacanoğlu et al. (2009) indicated that heavier chicks are produced from large-sized eggs (72.1-82.0 g) rather than medium-sized eggs (62.1-72 g) in broiler breeders. Egg water loss was reported to be related to egg weight between large eggs from post-peak broiler breeders and small eggs from young broiler breeders (Reis et al. 1997). In addition, breeder age affects egg characteristics (Latour et al. 1998; Lapao et al. 1999; Luquetti et al. 2004). Present studies have indicated that weights of yolk and albumen and yolk weight to albumen weight ratio increased, (O’Sullivan et al, 1991), and eggshell weight and eggshell conductance decreased (Luquetti et al. 2004; O’dea et al. 2004) with advancing breeder age. Tona et al. (2001) found that the highest quality of hatching eggs are produced by broiler breeder hens at 40 to 42 weeks of age. In addition, Tona et al. (2001) suggested that eggs laid by young, medium, or old breeders may be incubated under different conditions in order to improve hatchability and optimal incubation conditions. In fact, O’Dea et al. (2004) reported that embryonic metabolism is increased by advanced parental flock age. Embryonic metabolic demands during incubation may lead to the development of specific incubation conditions for different flock ages (Hamidu et al. 2007).

The aim of this study was to determine the effects of flock age of broiler breeder on incubating egg characteristics, egg water loss, total incubation length and chick development at hatching.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental design and incubation procedures

A total of 500 eggs were obtained from a broiler breeder stock (Ross 308) at 5 ages of broiler breeders; 30, 40, 43, 51 and 57 weeks of age were used in the experiment. Breeders from the same farm were fed with same diet and maintained under similar environmental conditions. Eggs from the 5 breeder ages were divided equally into 5 groups (100 eggs/breeder age). Incubating egg weights of each breeder age were determined as 55.3 g for 30 weeks of age, 62.1 g for 40 weeks of age, 62.6 g for 43 weeks of age 67.1 g for 51 weeks of age and 70.5 g for 57 weeks of age. All eggs were numbered for each groups as 4 replicates (25 eggs/ replicate/ breeder age) and placed into single-stage

incubators. Eggs from each broiler breeder age were incubated at specific dry-bulb temperature of 37.8°C and relative humidity of 60 %. The eggs were turned automatically every 90 minutes at a 45° angle on a daily basis until the 18th day of incubation. On the 18th day of incubation, the eggs were candled and living embryos were transferred to the hatcher.

Traits measured

Prior to incubation, randomly selected other 8 eggs from per age (8 eggs/breeder age) were used to measure the weights of egg (g), albumen (%), yolk (%) and eggshell (%) and, eggshell thickness (μ), egg shape index (%), yolk index (%) and albumen index (%), and eggshell weight per unit of surface area (mg/cm²) (Peebles and Mcdaniel, 2004). The ratio of the weights yolk and albumen was calculated. Yolk, albumen and eggshell (dried shell plus membranes) weights were given as percentages of egg weight. Indexes of egg shape, yolk and albumen were determined by using the formula below:

Egg shape index = [egg width (mm) / egg length (mm)] x 100

Albumen index = [albumen height (mm) / (albumen width + albumen length) (mm)] x 100

Yolk index = [yolk height (mm) / yolk diameter (mm)] x 100

Eggshell weight per unit of surface area was calculated as:

Eggshell weight per unit of surface area = [eggshell weight (mg) / eggshell surface area (cm²)],
where eggshell surface area = $3.9782 \times EW^{0.7056}$ (Basenko et al., 2005)

All eggs were individually weighed in order to calculate relative egg water loss as below.

Relative egg water loss = [(egg weight at day 0– egg weight at day 18 of incubation) / egg weight at day 0] x 100

Eggs were individually checked for every 3 hour between 450 and 520 hours of incubation, so the number of embryos pipping externally and chicks hatched were recorded. External pipping and hatching times were determined.

A total of 24 chicks, randomly 8 chicks from each replicate of breeder age groups were removed from the hatcher. Chick lengths (cm) and weights (g) were measured (Willemsen et al., 2008).

Statistical analyses

The data were analyzed by using the JMP Statistic Package (SAS Institute, 2007). One-way ANOVA was performed to analyze the effect of breeder age. Statistical significance was based on $P < 0.05$. The differences between the means for each breeding age group were compared using a Student-t test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Egg weight increased significantly with breeder age (Table 1). Proportional albumen weight and eggshell weight per unit of surface area were higher while proportional yolk weight and yolk weight to albumen weight ratio were lower in eggs from breeders 30 weeks of age than in eggs from other breeder ages (Table 1). Proportional eggshell weight was obtained the highest at 30 weeks of age and the lowest at 57 weeks of age (Table 1). Eggshell thickness decreased as numerically with breeder age, but it was not statistically significant ($P = 0.057$). Breeder age had no effect on indexes of egg shape and albumen (Table 1). Yolk index declined with breeder age and it was observed the lowest in breeders at 51 and 57 weeks of age (Table 1).

Table 1. Least means (\pm SEM¹) for weights of egg (g), albumen (%), yolk (%), eggshell (%), yolk weight to albumen weight ratio, eggshell thickness (μ), eggshell weight per unit of surface area (mg/cm²) and Indexes of egg shape (%), albumen (%) and yolk (%) by breeder age groups

Breeder age	Egg weight	Albumen weight	Yolk weight	Yolk weight/Albumen weight	Eggshell weight	Eggshell thickness	Eggshell weight per unit of surface area	Egg shape index	Albumen index	Yolk index
	g	%	%		%	μ m	mg/cm ²	%	%	%
30	55.3 \pm 0.3 _d	59.0 \pm 0.7 ^a	28.5 \pm 0.5 _b	0.48 \pm 0.01 _b	12.7 \pm 0.2 ^a	37.2 \pm 0.6	79.2 \pm 0.9 _a	77.5 \pm 0.7	82.7 \pm 1.8	46.9 \pm 0.7 _a
40	62.1 \pm 0.2 _c	56.5 \pm 0.5 ^b	31.3 \pm 0.4 _a	0.55 \pm 0.01 _a	11.8 \pm 0.1 ^b	36.8 \pm 0.5	75.4 \pm 0.8 _b	77.6 \pm 0.6	85.2 \pm 1.4	43.0 \pm 0.6 _b
43	62.6 \pm 0.2 _c	56.8 \pm 0.5 ^b	31.0 \pm 0.4 _a	0.54 \pm 0.01 _a	12.0 \pm 0.1 ^b	36.4 \pm 0.5	75.1 \pm 0.8 _b	77.0 \pm 0.6	85.4 \pm 1.4	43.5 \pm 0.6 _b
51	67.1 \pm 0.3 _b	56.9 \pm 0.7 ^a	31.5 \pm 0.6 _a	0.56 \pm 0.01 _a	11.6 \pm 0.2 ^b	35.7 \pm 0.7	74.9 \pm 1.0 _b	75.6 \pm 0.7	88.2 \pm 2.0	40.6 \pm 0.8 _c
57	70.5 \pm 0.2 _a	56.3 \pm 0.5 ^b	32.2 \pm 0.5 _a	0.57 \pm 0.01 _a	11.4 \pm 0.1 ^c	35.1 \pm 0.5	75.7 \pm 0.9 _b	76.0 \pm 0.6	85.6 \pm 1.3	39.6 \pm 0.6 _c
ANOVA	<.0001	0.026	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001	0.057	0.007	0.168	0.243	<.0001

^{a,b,c} Means in the same column with no common superscript differ significantly (P < 0.05). ¹SEM: Standard error of means.

On the 18th day of incubation, egg water loss ranged 11.1%, 12.3%, 8.04%, 10.6% and 11.5 % at 30, 40, 43, 51 and 57 weeks of age, respectively (Figure 1). Egg water losses were significantly higher in eggs from breeders at 30 weeks of age and 40 weeks of age, whereas it was significantly lower in eggs from breeders at 43 weeks of age than in eggs from the other breeders ages (Figure 1). Egg water loss was found similar between 51 and 57 weeks of age (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Least means (\pm SEM) for egg water loss (%) by breeder age groups (P<.0001) ^{a,b,c} Means at breeder age with no common superscript differ significantly (P < 0.05).

Breeder age significantly affected external pipping and hatching times (Figures 2; 3). The longest external pipping time was obtained from eggs at weeks 30 and 51 of age, while the shortest external pipping time was obtained from eggs at weeks 40 and 57 of age (Figure 2). On the other hand, there were no significant differences between 30 and 51 weeks of age. Hatching time was observed

the shortest at the ages of 40 and 57 weeks (Figure 2). The difference between total incubation length and external pipping time was 10.5 h for 30 weeks of age, 13.1 h for 40 weeks of age, 11.4 h for 43 weeks of age, 15.4 h for 51 weeks of age, and 13.3 h for 57 weeks of age ($P < .0001$).

Figure 2. Least means (\pm SEM) for external pipping time (hour) by breeder age groups ($P < .0001$)
^{a,b,c} Means at breeder age. with no common superscript differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Least means (\pm SEM) for hatching time (hour) by breeder age groups ($P < 0.0001$)

^{a,b,c} Means at breeder age with no common superscript differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

As the age of the breeding stock increases, chick length increases; however, chick length has remained similar in the age ranges of 40–43 and 51–57 weeks (Table 2). The lowest chick weight was observed in eggs laid by 30-week-old breeders, while the highest chick weight was observed in chicks hatched from eggs laid by 57-week-old breeders (Table 2).

Table 2. Least means (\pm SEM¹) for chick length and weight of chicks (g) by breeder age

Breeder age	Chick length		Chick weight	
		cm		g
30		18.1 \pm 0.1 ^c		40.4 \pm 0.9 ^d
40		18.9 \pm 0.1 ^b		46.8 \pm 0.8 ^c
43		18.8 \pm 0.1 ^b		47.1 \pm 0.8 ^c
51		19.1 \pm 0.1 ^a		47.4 \pm 0.9 ^b
57		19.3 \pm 0.1 ^a		48.6 \pm 1.2 ^a
Significance (P values)				
ANOVA		$P < .001$		$P < .001$

^{a,b,c,d} Means in the same column with no common superscript differ significantly ($P < 0.05$). ¹SEM: Standard error of means.

Discussion

There was a significant increase in egg weight and a decline in proportional eggshell weight with breeder age (30, 40, 43, 51 and 57 weeks of age), while no significant differences were observed in eggshell thickness. These results are consistent with egg weight, proportional eggshell weight and eggshell thickness reported in broiler breeder flocks from 30, 45 and 60 weeks of age (Luquetti et al. 2004). With the increasing breeder age, there was an increase in proportional yolk weight (65 > 42 > 32 weeks of age) (Yalçın et al., 2008), and a decrease in relative albumen weight (53 \geq 45 > 37 weeks of age) (O’dea et al., 2004). Concurrently, the yolk weight to albumen weight ratio increased (47 > 31 > 26 weeks of age) (Peebles et al., 2000). The present study found consistent effects on proportional yolk and albumen weights, and also on the yolk weight to albumen weight ratio. Furthermore, eggshell weight per unit of surface area declined due to increased egg weight with breeder age, as larger eggs have less shell area per unit of egg weight than smaller eggs from 30 weeks of age. The findings of the study demonstrated a general tendency towards a decline in the quality characteristics of the eggs,

while the weights of the egg and yolk, and the ratio of the weights of the yolk and albumen, increased with increasing breeder age.

The results of the present study indicated that the mean egg water loss of the eggs on the 18th d of incubation was 11.1% and 11.5 %, corresponding approximately to the optimal water loss prescribed by Tullett (1984), for 30 and 57 weeks of age. It has been observed that as the age of breeding hens increases, the water loss of eggs did not increase proportionally. This study suggests that there is a relationship between water loss in eggs and incubation period, based on the following explanations. In the study, the shorter external pipping time and incubation duration observed in eggs from 57-week-old broiler breeders may be related to optimal water loss during incubation in eggs from breeders of this age. It can be pointed that, in the context of the observed relationship, there is the potential for the attainment of shorter external pipping time and incubation duration in middle-aged flocks. Suarez et al. (1997) found that incubation time decreased with the effect of increased breeder age. Reis et al. (1997) stated that hatching times were not affected by the age of the hens. As outlined in previous studies, the differences found are indicative of partially attributable variations in egg water loss during the incubation process, which may be associated with eggshell quality.

As demonstrated by Tona et al. (2005), the age of broiler breeders has a substantial impact on the quality of hatching eggs and the subsequent development of chicks. This, in turn, affects the quality and weight of chicks hatched from these eggs.

The egg weight has been shown to have a significant impact on the hatching weight of the chick, due to the fact that the primary effect of egg weight is on the weight of the residual yolk sac that the chick retains at hatching (Williams, 1994). As noted by Shanawany (1984), egg weight increases with the age of breeding hens, and on day 21, chick weight is highly correlated with egg weight. [Shanawany, 1984; Suarez et al., 1997]. The results of this study confirmed these relationships, showing that, on day 21, the weight of chicks hatched from eggs laid by 30-week-old breeding hens with the lowest egg weight was significantly lower. In addition, the findings of the study demonstrated that weight, hatched chicks from large eggs in 40 and 43 weeks of age and 51 and 57 weeks of age exhibited increases in a linear manner with increases in age of breeder hens. Similarly, Suarez et al. (1997) reported that hatch weight of broiler chicks increased in a linear manner with increases in age of breeder hens between 29 and 47 weeks of age and between 47 and 57 weeks of age. When incubated under the same conditions, the primary reason for the weight difference between chicks from younger breeding flocks and those from older breeding flocks may be metabolic differences. Indeed, this interpretation is supported by O’dea et al. (2004)

It is generally accepted that larger chicks tend to be longer. This is supported by the findings of this study, which revealed that chicks from weeks 57 were the longest. The results indicate that chicks obtained from 30 week-old breeding hens had shorter in body length and a longer incubation period compared to those obtained from mid-old and older breeding hens. A similar manner, Babacanoglu et al. (2007) reported that chicks from older breeders were longer. These may be critical factors limiting the performance of chicks obtained from young broiler breeding hens. Indeed, O’Dea et al. (2004) reported that embryonic metabolism is increased by advanced parental flock age. As Hamidu et al. (2007) have argued, the metabolic demands of the embryo during the incubation period may result in the establishment of distinct incubation conditions for various flock ages.

CONCLUSION(S)

The age of broiler breeders alters the weights and characteristics of hatching eggs and affects the incubation duration and chick development during incubation Therefore, in conclusion, the management of egg incubation can be performed with consideration for the age of the breeders.

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Declaration of interests

The author declares no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Babacanoğlu, E., Güler, H. C., Aktaş, A. & Yalçın, S. (2007). The effects of breeder age and egg water loss on embriyo development and some physiological parameters in broiler breeders. Proceedings of 5th The National Animal Science Congress, 05-08 September, Van, Türkiye.
- Babacanoğlu, E., Aktaş, A. & Yalçın, S. (2009). Effects of egg weight on eggshell temperature, hatching performance, chick development and body composition. Proceedings of 6th The National Animal Science Congress, 24-26 June, Erzurum, Türkiye.
- Basenko, E. Y., Peebles, E. D., Branton, S. L., Whitmarsh, S. K. & Gerard, P. D. (2005). Effects of S6-strain mycoplasma gallisepticum inoculation at ten, twenty-two, or forty-five weeks of age on the performance characteristics of commercial egg laying hens. *Poultry Science*, 84, 1663–1670. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/85.11.2012>
- Hamidu, J. A., Fasenکو, G. M., Feddes, J. J. R., O’Dea, E. E., Ouellette, C. A., Wineland, M. J. & Christensen, V. L. (2007). The effect of broiler breeder genetic strain and parent flock age on eggshell conductance and embryonic metabolism. *Poultry Science*, 86, 2420-2432. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2007-00265>
- Hudson, B. P., Fairchild, B. D., Wilson, J. L., Dozier, W. A. & Buhr, R. J. (2004). Breeder age and zinc source in broiler breeder hen diets on progeny characteristics at hatching. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 13, 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/13.1.55>
- Lapao, C., Gama, L. T. & Soares, M. C. (1999). Effects of broiler breeder age and length of egg storage on albumen characteristics and hatchability. *Poultry Science*, 78, 640–645. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/78.5.640>
- Latour, M. A., Peebles, E. D., Boyle, C. R., Doyle, S. M., Pansky, T. & Brake, J. D. (1996). Effects of breeder hen age and dietary fat on embryonic and neonatal broiler serum lipids and glucose. *Poultry Science*, 75, 695–701. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.0750695>
- Latour, M. A., Peebles, E. D., Doyle, S. M., Pansky, T., Smith, T. W. & Boyle, C. R. (1998). Broiler breeder age and dietary fat influence the yolk fatty acid profiles of fresh eggs and newly hatched chicks. *Poultry Science*, 77, 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/77.1.47>
- Luquetti, B. C., Gonzales, E., Bruno, L. D. G., Furlan, R. L. & Macari, M. (2004). Egg traits and physiological neonatal chick parameters from broiler breeder at different ages. *Brazilian Journal of Poultry Science*, 6(1), 13-17. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-635X2004000100002>
- Noy, Y. & Sklan, D. (1997). Posthatch development in poultry. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 6, 344-354. <https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/6.3.344>
- O’dea, E. E., Fasenکو, G. M., Feddes, J. J. R., Robinson, F. E., Segura, J. C., Ouellette, C. A. & Van Middelkoop, J. H. (2004). Investigating the eggshell conductance and embryonic metabolism of modern and unselected domestic avian genetic strains at two flock ages. *Poultry Science*, 83, 2059-2070. doi: 10.1093/ps/83.12.2059.
- O’Sullivan, N. P., Dunnington, E. A. & Siegel, P. B. (1991). Relationships among age of dam, egg components, embryo lipid transfer and hatchability of broiler breeder eggs. *Poultry Science*, 70, 2180–2185. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.0702180>
- Peebles, E. D., Doyle, S. M., Pansky, T., Gerard, P. D., Latour, M. A., Boyle, C. R. & Smith, T. W. (1999). Effects of breeder age and dietary fat on subsequent broiler performance. 1. Growth, mortality, and feed conversion. *Poultry Science* 78: 505-511. doi: 10.1093/ps/78.4.505.
- Peebles, E. D., Zumwalt, C. D., Doyle, S. M., Gerard, P. D., Latour, M. A., Boyle, C. R. & Smith, T. W. (2000). Effects of breeder age and dietary fat source and level on broiler hatching egg characteristics. *Poultry Science*, 79, 698–704. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/79.5.698>
- Peebles, E. D., Doyle, S. M., Zumwalt, C. D., Gerard, P. D., Latour, M. A., Boyle, C. R. & Smith, T. W. (2001). Breeder age influences embryogenesis in broiler hatching eggs. *Poultry Science*, 80, 272-277. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/80.3.272>

- Peebles, E. D. & Mcdaniel, C. D. (2004). A practical manual for understanding the eggshell structure of broiler hatching eggs and measurements of their quality understanding. Missisipi State University the Office of Agricultural Communications, Bulletin, 1139, 17760-17777.
- Reis, L. H., Gama, L. T. & Soares, M. C. (1997). Effects of short storage conditions and broiler breeder age on hatchability, hatching time and chick weights. *Poultry Science*, 76, 1459–1466. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/76.11.1459>
- SAS, (2002). *Statistical Analysis Systems User's Guide: Statistics*, SAS Institute, Inc. Raleigh, North Carolina, USA.
- Shanawany, M. M. (1984). The interrelationship between egg weight, parental age and embryonic size. *British Poultry Science*, 25, 449–455. DOI: 10.1080/00071668408454886
- Suarez, M. E., Wilson, H. R., Mather, F. B., Wilcox, C. J. & McPherson, B. N. (1997). Effect of strain and age of the broiler breeder female on incubation time and chick weight. *Poultry Science*, 76, 1029–1036. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/76.7.1029>
- Tona, K., Bamelis, F., Coucke, W., Bruggeman, V. & Decuypere, E. (2001). Relationship between broiler breeder's age and egg weight loss and embryonic mortality during incubation in large-scale conditions. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 10, 221–227. <https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/10.3.221>
- Tona, K., Onagbesan, O., De Ketelaere, B., Decuypere, E. & Bruggeman, V. (2004). Effects of age of broiler breeders and egg storage on egg quality, hatchability, chick quality, chick weight, and chick posthatch growth to forty-two days. *J Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 13, 10–18. <https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/13.1.10>
- Tona, K., Bruggeman, V., Onagbesan, O., Bamelis, F., Gbeassor, M., Mertens, K. & Decuypere, E. (2005). Day-old chick quality: Relationship to hatching egg quality, adequate incubation practice and prediction of broiler performance. *Avian and Poultry Biology Reviews*, 16(2), 109-119. DOI:10.3184/147020605783438787
- Tullett, S. G. (1984). The porosity of avian eggshell. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Physiology*, 78, 5-13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0300-9629\(84\)90083-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0300-9629(84)90083-5)
- Willemsen, H., Everaert, N., Witters, A., De Smit, L., Debonne, M., Verschuere, F., ... & Bruggeman, V. (2008). Critical assessment of chick quality measurements as an indicator of posthatch performance. *Poultry Science*, 87 (11), 2358-2366. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2008-00095>
- Williams, T. D. (1994). Intraspecific variation in egg size and egg composition in birds: Effects on offspring fitness. *Biology Revision*, 68, 35-39. DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-185x.1994.tb01485.x
- Yalçın, S., Çabuk, M., Babacanoğlu, E., Buyse, J., Decuypere, E. & Siegel, P. B. (2006). Heat acclimation during incubation and breeder age influences on hatching performance of broilers. XII. European Poultry Conference, 10-14 September, Verona, Italy.
- Yalçın, S., Çabuk, M., Bruggeman, V., Babacanoğlu, E., Buyse, J., Decuypere, E. & Siegel, P. B. (2008). Acclimation to heat during incubation. 1. Embryonic morphological traits, blood biochemistry, and hatching performance. *Poultry Science*, 87, 1219–1228. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2007-00435>
- Yannakopoulos, A. L. & Tserveni-Gousi, A. S. (1987). Relationship of parent's age, hatching egg weight, and shell quality to day-old chick weights as influenced by oviposition time. *Poultry Science*, 66, 829-833. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.0660829>